

The Rural Hedge

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A rural hedgerow bordering a meadow

The rural hedge is a mixed hedge composed of various tree and shrub species, mostly indigenous. It offers numerous benefits for the profitability and sustainability of farms, as well as for animal welfare.

Hedgerows act as windbreaks, helping to mitigate extreme temperatures, thereby protecting crops, and they provide shade for animals in the summer. They also contribute to the infiltration and filtration of rainwater, reducing soil erosion and promoting groundwater recharge. As true ecological corridors, they facilitate habitat connectivity and support the presence of crop auxiliaries and pollinators along field edges. Additionally, hedgerows help with carbon storage and enhance the aesthetics of the rural landscape.

Hedgerows also offer economic advantages as they can provide fruits or forage, and their pruning residues can be used for ramial chipped wood (RCW) or compost. Over the long term, they could also produce timber.

The choice of tree species should be adapted to local pedoclimatic conditions, functional goals, and the desired morphology. Multi-layered hedgerows, consisting of herbaceous, shrub, and tree layers, offer the greatest potential due to their heterogeneity and complexity. Fencing or protective sleeves can prevent damage caused by livestock and wildlife. Regular maintenance of the hedgerows is essential to preserve their functionality: pruning, thinning, and cutting should be carried out at the appropriate time to minimize impact on wildlife and plants. Finally, subsidies and financial aid are often available to support the establishment of hedgerows, enabling farmers to adopt agroforestry practices if they wish.

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